

CHARACTERISTICS AND ANALYSIS OF FACTORS AFFECTING BUSINESS

Israilov B.*doctor of economics, professor***Abstract**

The effectiveness of the system of relations between the state and business entities is a positive factor of the socio-economic situation in the country. No matter how optimal the state policy is for creating the necessary conditions for business entities, any economic policy will not be effective if the business entity does not organize its activities properly. In the article, the authors studied the issue of internal and external factors affecting the activity of business entities and expressed their attitudes.

Keywords: state, business, business entity, state economic policy, efficiency, factors, analysis, result.

INTRODUCTION. The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) program of the United Nations recommends that the poor, rich and middle-developed countries of the world focus their activities on improving the well-being of the population and ensuring the protection of our planet. Efforts to eradicate poverty require increasing economic activity in order to increase economic growth and address a

number of challenges, such as education, health, social protection and employment. For this, it is planned to double the share of production in the gross domestic product (GDP), for which countries will spend approximately 1.051 billion US dollars annually [1].

It is known that the main source of income of the budget is tax revenue (Tab.1).

1- Table

The share of tax revenues in the budget revenues of states, %

T / r	Countries	Share of tax revenues in the state budget, %
1.	USA	95.5
2.	Great Britain	90.0
3.	Belarus	90.0
4.	Bulgaria	45.0
5.	Germany	89.0
6.	Italy	80.0
7.	Russia	90.0
8.	Czechia	68.5
9.	Kazakhstan	83.0
10.	Kyrgyzstan	68.0
11.	Uzbekistan	94.0

Source: Prepared by the author based on information from <https://ru.wikipedia.org/wiki>.

Taxes are formed due to the redistribution of income of business entities in the order and norms established by the legislation.

Research methodology. Methods such as logical thinking, analysis, synthesis, comparison and grouping are used in order to conduct research on the topic and justify the results.

Analysis of literature on the topic. O.D.Yevseyev [2], I.I.Mazur, V.D.Shapiro [3], M.Robson, M.Ullakh [4], A.G.Rindin, G.A.Shamayev [5], M.Hammer, J.Champi [6] about organizations of business entities and their specific features, J.H.Martin [7], M. Porter, V. Millar [8], A V Radchenko [9] were studied in the works of scientists.

IIMazur and VDS Shapiro give opinions that the business process is a systematic closed process, M.Robson, M.Ullakhlar work system, M.Hammer, J.Champilar the stages of activity and its results, A.V. Radchenko gives the opinion that the organization's activities are aimed at making a profit.

The role of taxes in the formation of state revenues and theoretical issues of regulating tax relations A. Temur [10], A. Smith [11], D. Ricardo [12] were studied in classic works.

Problems of tax administration improvement, Sh.Toshmatov [13], T.Malikov [14], B.Israilov [15], B.Tashmurodova [16], N.Khaydarov [17], B.Ibragimov [18] it has also been studied in the research of Uzbek scientists.

The first group of analyzed authors focused only on the business process in their work. The second group of scholars describes their views on taxes and their role in the formation of the state budget and tax administration. In the studies, the specific characteristics of business entities and the need to support them were not sufficiently evaluated in the works of scientists. Analyzing the work of scientists, it is possible to observe the tendency to prioritize the interests of the state in the study of business and state relations.

In the framework of the article, we focused on the analysis of the role of factors related to business development due to the fact that the importance of business subjects in the life of the state and society is of great importance in the conditions of market relations.

Analysis and results. There are many factors affecting business activity, and they can be divided into economic, political, legal and technological factors. In order for a businessman or manager to ensure the

effectiveness of his activities, it is necessary to study and analyze each factor that affects the business result. Because management requires choosing the most

convenient option for business. Factors that affect the efficiency of business results are grouped into internal and external factors (Figure 1).

Figure 1. A group of factors affecting business results.

Internal factors affecting the business result are factors that occur in the subject and can be eliminated by his efforts. These factors are interrelated and are typical for any business entity. Such factors are an increase (decrease) in the amount of profit ; increase (decrease) in production volume ; increase (deterioration) of product quality ; increase (increase) in product cost p a ; affects the increase (decrease) in

the volume of product sales. The negative impact of these factors depends on the efforts of business entity managers to eliminate or reduce them. Scientifically correct organization of activities and constant efforts to solve problems can prevent the negative impact of these factors on business results. It is appropriate to study and analyze the composition of these factors into the following groups (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Classification of factors affecting business results i.

This group of factors affecting business activity:

- factors related to production;
- divided into factors not related to production.

The category of factors related to production includes the state of fixed assets, technologies, labor and financial resources. Factors unrelated to production are social issues of labor organization, personnel supply, and environmental protection.

Also, internal factors related to production are divided into extensive and intensive factors. Extensive factors are related to the increase in the level of quantity, in this case, the number of employees, the

number of equipment, and the amount of financial resources are additionally involved. Under the influence of intensive factors, a high result is achieved due to the level of productivity.

There are several views of scientists regarding the composition of factors influencing business activity and their interrelation [19-22]. It is not unbiased to consider the analysis of factors recommended by scientists.

The cultural level of entrepreneurial activity of business structures is reflected in their relations with the state, clients and competing business entities. The

final result of the business depends on compliance with the rules of ethics and culture of its organization. Business culture is part of the system of internal factors affecting the result of its activity. Therefore, it is necessary to study this issue.

Bankruptcy and inefficiency of business entities in today's consumer market is characterized by non-observance of the rules of business culture.

By culture, we usually mean dressing well, speaking well, being quiet and not talking loudly.

Organizational culture is a system of shared values, symbols, beliefs, and collective behaviors that motivate a team's actions to achieve goals.

Business culture in business entities is not a process that is formed in a day, two days or a week or month. It is the norms of ethics generally recognized by business structural structures, their members and accepted by the community in a certain period of time.

The organizational culture of a business entity is formed on the basis of the area where its purpose is located, the beliefs, views and corporate ethics of the main members of the team, and strict norms, principles, trust and values that are the basis of relations and interactions in the internal and external environment (Figure 3).

Figure 3. The environment for the formation of organizational culture of a business entity ¹.

Is manifested in the attitude of employees to each other, tasks and solving their personal life issues, as well as the approach of the business entity to these events and incidents.

Business organizational structures, their partners work based on these generally recognized rules in problematic situations that arise during their activities.

Adherence to these standards is mandatory for all employees and partners who recognize them.

The organizational culture of a business entity cannot be forced on employees. Organizational culture works well when it is consciously recognized by employees. Researchers believe that it is necessary to study the formation and change of organizational culture in business organizations in connection with the processes of organizational life stages.

The culture of a business entity begins to form from the time when the idea of its organization appears. During this period, the organizational culture is like a baby and requires more attention from those around it. During this period, the author has a high risk of making a mistake due to the height of his desire to put his idea into practice. At this stage of organizational culture, the ability of the head of the business entity to take risks

and the characteristics of valuing the opinion of others are important.

The second stage of the business entity's organizational culture occurs when its office architecture and team organization are not formed. This phase will consist of hardship, economic hardship and struggle for survival. Overcoming economic failure is the result of the organizational culture and cohesion of the business entity, and failure is a test and a lesson for future challenges.

After overcoming economic helplessness and failures, the next stage of growth of the organizational culture of the business entity begins. In the eyes of the market participants, the enterprise is not afraid of economic difficulties and temporary failures, but finds a positive solution with the unity of the team, and builds respect and trust in the business entity among customers. At this stage, the honest and responsible operation of the business entity determines its future. Because every mistake made at this stage causes doubts about the trust that has arisen in relation to the business entity. At this stage of the business entity's organizational culture, the relationship between the team and the management has not fully found its place.

¹ ACCA. "Invedeniye v finans y i upravleniye biznesom" (IFB). Textbook. Upravlenchesky uchet (Accountant and business). 2 KAPLAN PUBLISHING. 2019. Prepared on the basis of.

Therefore, employees try to assign responsibility to the leader, and the leader to the employees.

In modern business organizations, managers pay attention to empowering employees and increasing their responsibility in decision-making. At the growth stage of the organizational culture, the relationship between the business entity and the external environment can be harmful. Therefore, the business entity has to make many risks and mistakes at this stage.

The next stage of formation of organizational culture in a business entity is called "youth stage" in many literatures. At this stage, the business entity has to go through a long and painful period. The business entity transfers its powers to the employees and causes the renewal of the organizational structure. The success of this stage depends on the professionalism of the head of the business entity, and due to the measures taken by the head, a high degree of harmony and harmony is ensured in the business entity.

Effective completion of the youth stage brings the organizational culture of the business entity to the "flowering stage". This stage is the stage that ensures the interconnection of knowledge, goals, opportunities and means of achieving them. If the business entity does not rest on the success achieved at this stage, seeks to attract new forces and new opportunities, and always strives for renewal, its flowering stage will last. Otherwise, a stabilization phase occurs.

The "sustainability phase" begins when a business loses its cool, drunk from its heyday. At this stage, the allocation of funds for scientific research by the business entity is reduced and a simple development path is chosen. A business entity is limited to past successes, does not seek to innovate, and as a result, development stops.

The "Blooming" and "Stability" stages define the middle age of a business entity. During this period, documents are created that reinforce the slogans and culture of the business entity. At these stages, the business entity finds its place in society and the market.

After the "stage of stability", the stage of aristocratism in the life of a business entity begins. The specific features of this stage are manifested in the decrease in the allocation of funds for scientific research and the increasing attention to the issues of control and insurance and improvement. The image of the organization is represented by behavior, behavior and dress code. New innovations are not supported, as a result, employees act to survive, not the business entity. These circumstances mean that a new stage will occur in the business entity.

The new stage of the life process of a business entity is "initial bureaucracy". At this stage, the leader blames the employees for the failure of the business entity. Unemployment grows, the number of permanent employees decreases, employees are constantly renewed, and the management does not change. In the business entity, the number of cases of blaming each other increases, no one finds fault with himself. These situations complicate the life processes of the business entity and cause it to move to the last stage.

The last stage of the life cycle of a business entity is the stage of "bureaucracy and completion". At this

stage, the team loses trust in each other. Activity information is hidden by employees. The management does not pay attention to the negative impact of such situations on the business result. As a result, the values of the business organization are completely undermined, and these situations cause the business entity to go bankrupt or split up.

As a result of the analysis of the essence of the stages of the life process of a business entity, it is necessary to form an organizational culture and to constantly update it based on the development of society. Such an approach guarantees the long-term and stable operation of the business organization.

The specific characteristics of the organizational culture of a business entity are manifested in the following cases.

1. The employee's knowledge of his place in the business entity.

2. Accessibility and communication language.

3. These situations are expressed in written, verbal and non-verbal forms of communication, "right to call" and public relations.

4. Conversations can be carried out in such forms as abviateva, gestures, slang, depending on the characteristics of regions and industries.

5. Appearance, dress and behavior at work.

6. Habits, eating and drinking, traditions. Namely, Employee meal plan, bringing from home, using buffet cafe service, eating out, group meals. Eating habits of managers, department heads and employees.

7. Attitude and use of working time.

8. System of relations between team members. That is, the formation of a system of relations based on age, gender, status, scientific potential, knowledge, experience, level. Level of communication formality, availability of employee support and dispute resolution procedures.

9. Values in a business entity. What is possible and what is not possible. Valuable things in the business entity for employees.

8. Attitude to the behavior of employees.

10. What is employee trust aimed at? That is, employees trust the leader, the existence of a justice system. Relationships with team members, colleagues and clients.

11. The system of increasing the qualification and knowledge of the employee.

12. The possibility to increase one's knowledge and experience, the existence of conditions to support it.

13. Work ethic and incentive system. Creation of working conditions, proper distribution of duties.

In most business entities, the employee's internal culture and knowledge of his place are valued. In some business entities, the employee's disclosure of his mood is encouraged. But some employees work best when they work alone. In a business entity, employees who achieve a better positive result in cooperation can also be the majority.

While employees are considered the main factor in shaping the organizational culture of a business entity,

organizational culture is created and shaped by managers and leaders.

The deterioration of the organizational culture of a business entity can also occur as a result of the actions of managers and leaders. The existence of the following situations in which a business entity has arisen as a result of the actions of managers and leaders can cause the decline of the organizational culture of a business entity:

- dissatisfaction of employees in the position of management;
- inability of managers to form the basic values of the workplace;

- absence of specific "slang" and "folklore" in the business entity;
- use of intimidation methods in labor orientation;
- how to motivate individual employees.

Formation of an organizational culture, which deals with these situations and ensures the solution of priority tasks and career growth, protects the business entity from decline.

External factors affecting business activity and its result are factors independent of the entity (Figure 4).

Figure 4. General classification of external factors affecting business results

These factors directly and indirectly affect the business result. This group of factors consists of a number of factors, each of which affects the business result. Therefore, it is appropriate to classify their

content accordingly for analysis. For example, the general structure of the economic factors included in this group can be seen in the diagram below (Fig. 5).

Figure 5. Classification of the composition of the group of economic factors affecting business.

We believe that the impact of these factors on business results should be determined using economic analysis methods and SVOT analysis. The influence of factors is calculated based on the methods recommended by scientists. Timely delivery of necessary and important information for management is one of the main tasks of the analysis. Appropriate

management decisions are made based on the impact of each factor on the current and past business results.

Conclusions and suggestions. In addition, there are factors of a private nature that affect business activity. When starting a business and running it, it is appropriate for a businessman to analyze the impact of additional ecological, ethical and demographic factors

on the business result along with the main factors. A factor that usually seems insignificant to us can have a more positive or negative impact on the business result.

The political environment in a country can affect business activities in various ways. This situation leads to increased risk and loss. Therefore, political factors affect the results of business activities, as well as the policies of the government and local authorities. Therefore, when organizing his activities, a businessman needs to analyze the local and international political situation and, based on the results of the analysis, find ways of cooperation for his business.

Changes in public policy can also cover economic, legal and social spheres. For example, the state may change tax rates and bases based on the political views of the ruling party, or give tax payers benefits and preferences. Therefore, a businessman should not forget in making every decision that political decisions in society can affect the economic, legal, social, cultural environments and technological development processes.

Using these recommendations will extend the life of the business and ensure capital efficiency.

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